

Studies on the sorption of Zn^{II} on the synthetic gel sodium potassium fluorophlogopite

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Abstract : Sorption of Zn^{II} has been studied on the synthesized gel, sodium potassium fluorophlogopite [Na_{0.5}K_{0.5}Mg₃(Si₃AlO₁₀)F₂.6H₂O] (SPFP) at pH 2, 4 and 7. The effect of parameters like equilibration time (0.5–24.0 h), weight of the exchanger (30–150 mg) and temperature (25–45 °C) have been investigated. The uptake of the metal ion Zn^{II} has been expressed in terms of distribution coefficient (*K_d*).

Keywords : Sorption, zinc, synthetic gel.

Contamination of environment by heavy metals is of growing concern because of health risks posed by human and animal exposure. The common methods of removal of metal ions include various chemical processes such as chemical precipitation, solvent extraction, electro dialysis, electrolytic extraction, and reverse osmosis, biosorption etc.¹. The development of synthetic inorganic materials with higher selectivity of ions has received much attention during the last two decades². A study of the several materials reported shows that the mica group of minerals has not been studied much. It was, therefore, thought of interest to study the sorption of Zn^{II} on one of the mica group of minerals, sodium potassium fluorophlogopite Na_{0.5}K_{0.5}Mg₃(Si₃AlO₁₀)F₂.³

Experimental

The mica mineral, sodium potassium fluorophlogopite was synthesized by the hydrothermal method in a Teflon-lined stainless steel pressure vessel at a temperature 200 °C for 72 h by literature method⁴. The chemical composition of the synthesized gel was checked by elemental analysis using energy dispersive spectrometry (EDS).

The XRD pattern of the gel was recorded on a computer interfaced PW 3011 (mini prop.) diffractometer system, while the EDS pattern of the gel was recorded (EDAXZAF quantification) at "SICART", Vallabh Vidyanagar, Gujarat. A weighed amount of this gel was equilibrated with required concentrations of Zn^{II} ions at pH 2, 4 and 7. The exchanger was also equilibrated with Zn^{II} solution in a ther-

mostated water bath at 25, 35 and 45 °C. There six sets of experiments are performed for each study.

The selectivity of Zn^{II} ions by this gel is expressed in terms of distribution coefficient i.e. *K_d*, which is defined as :

$$K_d = \frac{C_i - C_e}{C_e} \times \frac{V}{w} \text{ ml/g}$$

where, *C_i* = initial concentration of metal ion, *C_e* = equilibrium concentration of metal ion, *V* = volume of solution in milliliter and *w* = weight of exchanger (SPFP) in grams.

Table 1. Chemical composition of synthesized gel (SPFP) obtained from EDS analysis

Composition	Wt. (%)	At (%)	K-Ratio	Z	A	F
OK	46.46	59.51	0.1306	1.0250	0.2747	1.0007
NaK	2.47	2.20	0.0070	0.9605	0.2928	1.0066
MgK	12.58	10.60	0.0495	0.9857	0.3964	1.0080
AlK	5.98	4.54	0.0229	0.9578	0.3955	1.0113
SiK	29.71	21.68	0.1363	0.9867	0.4648	1.0005
KK	2.80	1.47	0.0199	0.9348	0.7594	1.0000

Results and discussion

Characterization :

The EDS analysis and X-ray diffraction suggest that the gel is similar to the fluorine mica, sodium potassium fluorophlogopite Na_{0.5}K_{0.5}Mg₃(Si₃AlO₁₀)F₂.6H₂O. X-Ray powder diffraction pattern (Fig. 1) of the sample shows maxima at 36.68 counts/s, *d*-spacing : 1.53347 Å, relative intensity (%) : 100.00, angle : (2θ = 60.30612), background

Table 2. Weight variation study of SPFP for Zn^{II}

Temp. = 25 °C, pH of the solution = 7.0, equilibration time = 8.0 h

Wt. of the exchanger (mg)	Initial concentration of Zn ^{II} mmols in 50 ml	Zn ^{II} in solid phase mmols	Zn ^{II} remaining in solution after equilibration mmols/50 ml	K _d (ml/g)						Mean	Standard deviation $\sqrt{\frac{\sum(x-\bar{x})^2}{n-1}}$
				(i)	(ii)	(iii)	(iv)	(v)	(vi)		
30	0.468	0.143	0.325	219.92	219.98	220.12	220.00	220.32	220.36	220.12	0.1852
60	0.468	0.155	0.313	247.44	247.42	247.78	247.60	247.52	247.82	247.60	0.1703
90	0.468	0.161	0.307	262.19	262.15	262.31	262.23	262.51	262.47	262.31	0.1496
100	0.468	0.324	0.144	1124.92	1124.82	1125.00	1124.94	1125.12	1125.16	1125.00	0.1179
120	0.468	0.331	0.137	1208.31	1208.39	1208.34	1208.49	1208.51	1208.30	1208.39	0.0909
150	0.468	0.338	0.130	1299.95	1299.92	1299.93	1300.00	1300.12	1300.08	1300.00	0.0832

Fig. 1. X-Ray diffractograms of hydrothermally synthesized SPFP gel.

Table 3(a). Thermodynamic study of Zn^{II} sorbed by SPFP

Equilibration time = 8.0 h, pH of the solution = 7.0, weight of the exchanger = 100 mg

Initial conc. of Zn ^{II} (M)		25 °C				35 °C				45 °C			
Concn. of the solution Zn ^{II} (M)	mmols of Zn ^{II} in 50 ml	Zn ^{II} in solid phase total mmols	Zn ^{II} remaining in solution after equi. mmols/50 ml	K _d (ml/g)	ΔG (kcal)	Zn ^{II} in solid phase total mmols	Zn ^{II} remaining in solution after equilibration mmols/50 ml	K _d (ml/g)	ΔG (kcal)	Zn ^{II} in solid phase total mmols	Zn ^{II} remaining in solution after equilibration mmols/50 ml	K _d (ml/g)	ΔG (kcal)
0.01	0.468	0.324	0.144	1125.00	-0.730	0.330	0.138	1195.65	-0.89	0.355	0.113	1570.70	-1.28
0.02	0.936	0.637	0.299	1065.20	-0.480	0.652	0.284	1147.88	-0.71	0.727	0.209	1739.20	-0.96
0.04	1.872	1.056	0.815	648.46	-0.031	1.109	0.763	726.73	-0.62	1.155	0.717	805.43	-0.83
0.05	2.340	0.440	1.900	115.78	0.028	0.556	1.784	155.80	-0.53	0.739	1.601	230.79	-0.71
0.10	4.680	0.690	3.990	86.46	-0.021	0.900	3.780	119.04	-0.41	1.190	3.490	170.48	-0.46

Table 3(b). Acid variation studies for Zn^{II} on the SPFP

Equilibration time = 8.0 h, temp. = 25 °C, weight of the exchanger = 100 mg

Initial concn. of Zn ^{II} (M)		pH 7.0			pH 4.0			pH 2.0		
Concn. of the solution Zn ^{II} (M)	mmols of Zn ^{II} in 50 ml	Zn ^{II} in solid phase mmols	Zn ^{II} remaining in solution after equilibration mmols/50 ml	K _d (ml/g)	Zn ^{II} in solid phase total mmols	Zn ^{II} remaining in solution after equilibration mmols/50 ml	K _d (ml/g)	Zn ^{II} in solid phase total mmols	Zn ^{II} remaining in solution after equilibration mmols/50 ml	K _d (ml/g)
0.01	0.468	0.324	0.144	1125.00	0.301	0.167	944.48	0.278	0.190	731.57
0.02	0.936	0.637	0.299	1065.20	0.594	0.342	868.40	0.484	0.452	535.39
0.04	1.872	1.056	0.815	648.46	0.992	0.880	563.67	0.639	1.233	259.12
0.05	2.340	1.811	0.529	171.05	1.110	1.230	451.23	0.920	1.420	323.94
0.10	4.680	3.670	1.010	137.60	2.013	2.667	377.36	1.818	2.862	317.60

(count/s) : 86.66 and significance : 103. The EDS analysis of the synthetic gel (Table 1 and Fig. 1) suggest that estimated weight percentage values agree very well with the weight percentage of these metal ions taken [Na, K, Mg, Al and Si]. Presence of H₂O molecules associated with the gel

The SPFP gel shows separation of the two hexagonal by a distance of 1.53347 Å. Thus the structural investigation shows that the hydrothermal phase resembles disordered potassium fluorophlogopite phase, which may gradually be ordered to 1 M type. The ordering of phase begins at 425 °C

Fig. 2. TGA graph of hydrothermally synthesized SPFP gel

is confirmed from its FTIR spectrum, a strong and broad peak between 3200–3600 cm⁻¹ for OH stretching and a strong and sharp peak between 1200–1500 cm⁻¹ for the OH bending frequency. The exact number of water molecules bound in the gel was ascertained by thermogravimetric analysis; the TGA graph shows (Fig. 2) 20.80% weight loss, which corresponds to 6H₂O molecules.

below which the mineral exists in a gel like phase. Sheet structure of fluorine mica as made up of a hexagonal network with the hexagonal vacant sites available for the exchange of ions.

K_d values for Zn^{II} increases with time up to 7 h after which it remains constant, therefore time required for equilibrium for further studies was taken as 8 h. K_d values in-

creased with increase in exchanger composition due to the availability of more number of active sites for exchange⁵ Studies with different amounts of the gel (30–150 mg) showed that 100 mg of the exchanger (1 : 500) was sufficient for optimum exchange (Table 2). Six measurements were made with each weight of the exchanger. The K_d values closely resembles with each other and also the standard deviation is found to be very small. Standard deviation decreases with increase in weight of the exchanger which is obvious. However, for further studies the weight of the exchanger was taken as 100 mg. Sorption studies were carried out at varying temperature (25–45 °C) and pH (2, 4 and 7), Tables 3(a) and 3(b), respectively. Highest value of K_d was obtained at pH 7. It is also observed that K_d value increases with temperature. Increase in temperature enhances exchange of ion in aqueous solution as the thermal agitation of the system, processes such as association of ions, aggregation, ion pairing and complex formation are discouraged in the system⁶. The negative value of ΔG with rise in temperature also supports for better exchange at higher temperature.

Thus it can be concluded that the synthetic ion exchanger, sodium potassium fluorophlogopite, has a great

potential for Zn^{II} sorption at pH 7, and it can be very well applied to Zn ion separation from industrial waste water.

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